

Standards of developing study program. An example of Polish legislation in higher education.

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Abstract

Turbulent business environment requires employees to have skills adjusted to changing economic conditions. A potential employee should plan his or her education so that acquired knowledge allows them to be agile. Additionally, the fourth industrial revolution and more specifically assumptions thereof underline employment of persons with both, high competences strictly dictated by the job position, so-called hard skills, and soft skills, that is, social and interpersonal skills. Such a situation forces educational institutions to develop curricula so that acquired competences correspond with the market needs. The article presents the proposition of developing curricula for higher education. The process of developing the conception of curriculum constituting the element of developing faculties has been presented herein. The practical dimension of the article is based on the solutions binding in the European legislation and experiences resulting from participation in projects.

Keywords: Curriculum; education; Industry 4.0; Project Approaches.

1 Introduction

Developing the curriculum results from the need of implementation thereof and the demand therefor. Such an impulse may be given by both, a business entity, as well as a teaching employee or even an interested student. Irrespectively of a person indicating the need to develop the curriculum, it is important for all stakeholders (both, internal and external to the same extent) to support legitimacy of development thereof. The literature describing the rules of developing curricula mainly comprises national legal acts (acts and ordinances – in Poland it is the Ministry/Minister of Science and Higher Education (MNiSW; Act 2.0), European norms/practices (European Commission, 2007; European Higher Education Area and Bologna Process (EHEA) and requirements of institutions verifying and certifying the education process at a university (Polish Accreditation Committee (PKA), National Education Systems (EACEA); European Quality Assurance Register for Higher Education (EQAR); "University of Leaders" (UL); "Studies with Future" or "Education Quality Leader" (SzP). Additional and very valuable sources of information comprise many published solutions in the scope of developing curricula implemented by universities or scientific articles describing so-called "educational trends".

The education system must fulfil high standards so that the shared knowledge and acquired skills described by Lima et al., (2017) and Ayen & Nitkiewicz (2018), correlate with industrial needs. Therefore, continuous control of the education system, that is, the education quality, is important. One can read about such solutions in publications by Ulewicz (2017), Ulewicz et al. (2020) and Nitkiewicz et al. (2019), Klimecka-Tatar et al. (2014) and Ulewicz & Sethanan (2019). Continuous improvement of curricula due to the use of e.g. distance education techniques described by Jelonek et al. (2014), Wysłocka (2015) and Dudek & Kulej-Dudek (2016), is very important in the era of remote work and distance learning. The use of such opportunities allows implementation of the assumption of balanced development in order to ensure economic viability, systematic education and environmental balance (Zawada et al., 2016; Pisut et al., 2019), as well as the future of education (Jelonek et al., 2015). Furthermore, it is important to adjust education to the requirements of the fourth industrial revolution Industry 4.0, described by Wiśniewska-Sałek (2014), so that the qualifications of graduates correspond with the labour market needs and constitute a response thereto. Thus, it may be stated that, as presented by Wiśniewska-Sałek with co-authors (2019), an employee becomes Employee 4.0.

2 Legal aspects of developing curricula in Poland

The basic requirement that should be met in order to start the procedure of developing curriculum, in compliance with the Act on Higher Education (Dz.U., 2018a), is education in the scientific fields and disciplines adopted by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). The University assigns the faculty to at least 1 discipline and establishing studies at a given faculty, level and profile requires a permit issued by the Minister of Science and Higher Education. Whereas, agreeing on the curriculum requires consultations with the student government. Studies of a specific faculty may be conducted in a form of full-time and/or part-time studies (conditions that should be met respectively are as follows: at least half of ECTS points/less than a half of ECTS points covered with the curriculum should be obtained within studies with a direct participation of academic teachers).

The level of the studies distinguishes: (i) first cycle degree studies, (ii) second cycle degree studies and (iii) long-cycle Master's degree programme. The duration of particular levels is the following: (i) at least 6 semesters (and in the case of obtaining engineering competences at least 7 semesters), (ii) from 3 to 5 semesters and (iii) from 9 to 12 semesters. There is a possibility of prolonging this period of time in the case of part-time studies.

The profile of students is a practical profile that, according to the name, develops students' practical skills and general academic profile, where classes are related to the academic activity conducted at the university. Furthermore, the practical profile assumes the students' necessity to complete internship for a period of 6 months by first cycle degree students and long-cycle Master's degree students and a period of 3 months by second cycle degree students. Additionally, the Polish legislation provides for the possibility of education at postgraduate studies (at least 3 semesters – obtaining full qualifications at 6th, 7th or 8th level of the Polish Qualifications Framework "PQF" (Dz.U., 2016) and providing specialist education (at least 3 semesters – obtaining full qualifications at 5th level of the PQF: classes developing practical skills).

The curriculum specifies: learning effects, description of the process leading to obtaining learning effects and the number of ECTS points attributed to specific classes (ECTS point = 25-30 hours of student's work). Also classes conducted with the use of distance education methods and techniques. In the case of curricula preparing to studies in the professions: a doctor, a dentist, a pharmacist, a nurse, a midwife, a laboratory diagnostician, a physiotherapist, a paramedical practitioner, a veterinarian, an architect or a teacher, it is required to adjust them to educational standards.

One of the conditions of graduating studies comprises obtaining the learning effects specified in the curriculum for: first cycle degree studies – 180 ECTS points, second cycle degree studies – 90 ECTS points and for long-cycle Master's degree programme – 300 ECTS points (9-10 semesters) and 360 ECTS points (11-12 semesters). Another condition constitutes passing the diploma exam and positive assessment of the diploma thesis. A graduate is a student, who obtained the diploma of graduating studies at a particular faculty and profile. The diploma confirms obtaining higher education and professional title of: Bachelor, Engineer (first cycle degree studies); Master, Master Engineer (second cycle degree studies and long-cycle Master's degree programme). In the case of specialist education it is a certificate of a certified specialist or a certificate of a certified specialist technologist.

3 Quality of education – evaluation compliant with the Polish law

In the Polish legislation a body providing evaluation in the form of curriculum assessment or complex assessment is the Polish Accreditation Committee (PKA). The complex assessment (which will be binding as of October 2020) is conducted upon the request of the university, which has only positive curriculum assessment. The idea of complexity refers to the assessment of the effectiveness of measures undertaken to the benefit of ensuring the quality of education with regard to all fields in which the education is provided. Whereas, the curriculum programme concerns cyclical assessment of the quality of education at the faculty and concerns verification of: curricula; teaching and academic employees; infrastructure used in the educational process; cooperation with the socio-economic environment. Additionally, the degree of internationalisation and support provided for students in the learning process are also taken into consideration. This type of assessment is initiated by PKA upon the request of the university or the Minister. Evaluation of the quality is completed with

issuing a positive or negative assessment for a period of 6 years. A positive assessment or a refusal to issue a positive assessment is given in the complex assessment for a period of 3-8 years. Quality is evaluated on the grounds of the assessment, accreditation or certificate of the entity assessing the quality of education conducted by the Polish Accreditation Committee (PKA) or entered into the European Quality Assurance Register for Higher Education (EQAR).

3.1 New faculty (field of study)

At the Czestochowa University of Technology, pursuant to the Polish legislation, among others, the statute and the rules and regulations of studies at the University are binding in the process of developing a faculty (and thus, developing curricula). These documents hierarchize particular organisational units in order to give opinion on the relevance of developing a given faculty. The final decision on development, transformation or liquidation belongs to the rector upon his or her initiative or upon the request of the dean of the relevant department. The unit specifying the guidelines which should be fulfilled in the scope of developing and introducing changes to curricula is the University's Senate. Formally, this application has to be given an opinion by the Curriculum Board, Teaching Manager, Senate Committee and Student Government beforehand. Such a system is aimed at obtaining opinions of numerous environments in order to maximise the chance for successful implementation thereof. In the formal process of drawing up an application for developing a new faculty one should follow the binding application published by the Polish Accreditation Committee (the document is compliant with the guidelines included in the Ordinance of the Minister of Science and Higher Education (Dz.U., 2018b).

Apart from general characteristics, a formal application for establishing a faculty should also include: (i) conception of education (that is, relation between studies and the university's strategy, socio-economic needs and compliance thereof with the learning effects, as well as assigning the faculty to the scientific discipline); (ii) justification of establishing the studies; (iii) description of measures to the benefit of improving the curriculum and ensuring the quality of education; (iiii) description of conducted scientific activity in the discipline; (iiiii) description of competences expected from the candidate for studies; (iiiii) description of the terms and conditions of studies with the manner of organising and implementing the process leading to obtaining learning effects (the list of academic teachers proposed for conducting classes should be included); (iiiii) information regarding the infrastructure (that is, description of laboratories, workshops, devices and equipment, necessary for education); (iiiii) information regarding providing the possibility of using library resources and electronic knowledge resources (Virtual Science Library, Digital Rental of Academica Scientific Publications). Additionally, the following appendixes should be attached: (i) legal acts and rector's statements regarding establishing studies at a specific faculty, level and profile; (ii) planned schedule of implementing the curriculum (as divided into semesters and years of the education cycle); (iii) opinion of the student government on the curriculum; (iiii) academic teachers' declaration (employment term at the university and number of working hours); (iiiii) documentation confirming being at a disposal of relevant infrastructure; (iiiii) description of library resources and (iiiii) document confirming concluding an agreement with employers with regard to the acceptance of a specific number of students for internship. (PKA)

3.2 Curriculum

While starting work on the curriculum, the duration of a semester (15 weeks) should be taken into consideration in order to evenly plan the student's workload. Having assumed establishing studies in the field of social sciences and management and quality science discipline with general-academic profile at the level of full-time second cycle degree studies, while awarding the professional title of Master, in total 90 ECTS points should be assumed. Therefore, the curriculum should provide for obtaining by the student 30 ECTS points in each semester (90 ECTS/4 semesters).

While formulating the curriculum, developing a syllabus for the subject or a group of subjects should also be taken into account, irrespectively of the form of conducting such classes to which the learning effects and curriculum content ensuring obtaining such effects are assigned. A total number of hours of these classes as well as manners of verification and assessment of learning effects which will be obtained by the student during the whole learning cycle should be specified. Moreover, the total number of ECTS points should be given: (i) which the student has to obtain within the framework of classes conducted with the direct participation of an

academic teacher; (ii) which the student has to obtain within the framework of classes in the field of humanities or social sciences (at least 5 ECTS points); (iii) which the student has to obtain within the framework of this internship (together with specification of the scope, principles and form of completing internship). Furthermore, the curriculum should include: physical education classes (60 hours: 0 ECTS – for first cycle degree studies and long-cycle Master’s degree studies conducted in the form of full-time studies), the possibility to select classes which have been assigned with ECTS in the scope not lower than 30% of the number of ECTS points. Construction of classes within the curriculum should be compliant with the profile of studies: practical – developing practical skills; general-academic – preparing to conducting scientific activity (participation therein).

While establishing the curriculum one should assume a certain pattern of assigning ECTS points to subjects. While knowing that each semester is assigned with 30 ECTS (even workload of the student) and 1 or 2 hours of a given subject per week, the manner presented in table no. 1 can be assumed.

Table 1. Example extract from the curriculum (first semester), second cycle degree studies.

Number of ECTS points	Type of subject	exam/test	Student's workload	Type of classes
5	economic sciences	exam/test	125 h / 5 ECTS	2h - lecture 2h - exercises
5	engineer-technical sciences	exam/test	125 h / 5 ECTS	2h - lecture 3h - laboratory
5	quality sciences	exam/test	125 h / 5 ECTS	1h - lecture 2h - project 2h - laboratory
4	management sciences	test	100 h / 4 ECTS	1h - lecture 2h - project
4	IT sciences	test	100 h / 4 ECTS	1h - lecture 2h - laboratory
3	mathematics sciences	test	75 h / 3 ECTS	1h - lecture 1h - exercises
2	social sciences	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	2h - project
2	foreign language	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	2h - discussion session
30 ECTS			750 h / 30 ECTS	26 h (per week)

The number of hours of direct contact with the lecturer amounts to 50% of the time which student has to devote to learning curriculum content. Such a result of the indicator provides the possibility of working with the student (the possibility of explaining doubts) and the time to independently study thoroughly and acquire skills. Furthermore, the type of conducted classes is also important. The more project work (using one of the teaching methods Project Based Learning, described in the literature i.a. by Mesquita et al. (2018)) or laboratories are provided for in the curriculum, the more learning effects can be assumed by implementation thereof, through practical skills. New curricula should be focused on acquiring knowledge through its practical aspect.

Another important element is to establish the curriculum in the direction preparing the student to start employment at a specific business activity. The Polish legislation assumes that a student should be provided with a possibility to select subjects in the number corresponding with 30% of the total number of ECTS points. The university’s practice shows that two of the above factors can be ensured by introducing to the curriculum so-called education in the scope of e.g. economic faculty or otherwise educating in the scope of a specific specialty/specialisation. Then, it can be assumed that the first semester is a certain base of general faculty-related knowledge for second cycle degree studies. Whereas, the second semester assumes several general subjects and several subjects to choose from. Chosen subjects should be compliant with the offered education in the scope from the third semester. Main task thereof should constitute introducing a student to matters related to the specific specialty. So that he or she can consciously select (from the second year of studies in the case of second cycle degree studies and after the second year in the case of first cycle degree studies) what

they wish to specialise in, when they become a potential employee. Foreign language constitutes value added to each curriculum. In the first two semesters it is recommended to teach a foreign language so that e.g. the learnt vocabulary prepares to the profession of an engineer, an IT specialist or management staff. A detailed proposition of such a curriculum has been presented in table no. 2.

Table 2. Example extract from the curriculum (second semester), second cycle degree studies.

Number of ECTS points	Type of subject	exam/test	Student's workload	Type of classes
5	economic sciences	exam/test	125 h / 5 ECTS	2h - lecture 2h - exercises
5	engineer-technical sciences	exam/test	125 h / 5 ECTS	2h - lecture 3h - laboratory
5	management and quality sciences	exam/test	125 h / 5 ECTS	2h - lecture 2h - project
3	management sciences	test	75 h / 3 ECTS	2h - project 1h - exercises
2	subject in the scope of education (specialty A)	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	1h - lecture 1h - laboratory
2	subject in the scope of education (specialty B)	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	1h - lecture 1h - project
2	subject in the scope of education (specialty C)	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	1h - lecture 1h - exercises
2	mathematics sciences	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	2h - project
2	social sciences	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	2h - exercises
2	foreign language	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	2h - discussion session
30 ECTS			750 h / 30 ECTS	28 h (per week)

Another two semesters should include in their offer specialisation subjects in a foreign language. It provides the student with the future possibility of working in international teams. An important aspect, especially of the last year of studies, is the diploma thesis. Separation of the function of a supervisor (substantive supervision) and person conducting the seminar (formal supervision) should be underlined, since in the process of writing this type of thesis, a direct contact with the lecturer is especially important. The curriculum should also assume which subjects will allow introducing a student to the "world of science" such as e.g. scientific research methodology. Moreover, it is worth taking into account interdisciplinary subjects, which will broaden the student's horizons allowing him or her to look at certain patterns in a non-standard manner. Conducted subjects in the scope of mathematical sciences should take into consideration such learning effects so that a student can freely conduct analyses and be able to draw conclusions. Furthermore, subjects providing a student with a possibility of conducting their own research or engaging a student in scientific research conducted at the University's unit are also important. An example of such a curriculum has been provided for in table no. 3.

Table 3. Exemplary extract from the curriculum (third and fourth semester), second cycle degree studies for education in the scope of (specialty A).

Number of ECTS points	Type of subject	exam/test	Student's workload	Type of classes
third semester				
5	subject in the scope of education (specialty A)	exam/test	125 h / 5 ECTS	2h - lecture 2h - laboratory
5	subject in the scope of education (specialty A)	exam/test	125 h / 5 ECTS	2h - lecture 2h - project
4	subject in the scope of education (specialty A) in a foreign language	test	100 h / 4 ECTS	1h - lecture 1h - exercises
		test	100 h / 4 ECTS	1h - project 1h - lecture

4	subject in the scope of education (specialty A) in a foreign language			1h - exercises 1h - laboratory
3	subject in the scope of education (specialty A)	test	75 h / 3 ECTS	1h - project 1h - laboratory
3	scientific research methodology	test	75 h / 3 ECTS	1h - lecture 1h - project
2	diploma seminar I	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	2h - seminar
2	preparation to writing a diploma thesis I	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	2h - project
2	interdisciplinary subject	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	1h - lecture
30 ECTS			750 h / 30 ECTS	23 h (per week)
fourth semester				
5	subject in the scope of education (specialty A)	exam/test	125 h / 5 ECTS	2h - lecture 2h - laboratory
5	subject in the scope of education (specialty A)	exam/test	125 h / 5 ECTS	2h - lecture 2h - project
4	subject in the scope of education (specialty A) in a foreign language	test	100 h / 4 ECTS	1h - lecture 1h - exercises 1h - project 1h - lecture
4	subject in the scope of education (specialty A) in a foreign language	test	100 h / 4 ECTS	1h - exercises
3	scientific research methodology	test	75 h / 3 ECTS	2h - project
2	diploma seminar II	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	2h - seminar
5	preparation to writing a diploma thesis II	test	125 h / 5 ECTS	2h - project
2	interdisciplinary subject	test	50 h / 2 ECTS	1h - lecture
30 ECTS			750 h / 30 ECTS	20 h (per week)

It should be remembered while developing curricula for various specialties from the formal point of view to establish their mirror reflection. Such behaviour guarantees that each student obtains assumed learning effects to the same degree, irrespectively of the specialty binding at one faculty.

4 Conclusion

Developing a new faculty with the consideration of all formal procedures should be primarily justified with the labour market. The continuously developing industry in the era of adjusting and/or implementing assumptions of the fourth industrial revolution needs "Employee 4.0". Staff with specific specialist competences and high soft skills constitute a real challenge for the whole education system at each level of teaching.

Development of the faculty should constitute a response to the contemporary trends in the labour market and dynamic changes in the economy, society and technology. Furthermore, a faculty should be an answer to the changing employment systems (e.g. self-employment) and development of modern management techniques in organisations, both, small- and medium-sized companies, and large corporations. Therefore, participation of all economy participants in developing curriculum is so important.

A good example of such a co-participation is the project "Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry – MSIE4.0" (<https://msie4.ait.ac.th/>). One curriculum is developed by project contractors from 9 universities. During development of the curriculum, good practices in higher education from Thailand, Portugal, Romania and Poland were used. Then, a research was conducted among entrepreneurs (Chattinnawat, 2018a) and students (Chattinnawat, 2018b) in particular countries/universities. This activity was aimed at learning about preferences of internal and external stakeholders regarding educational needs adjusted to work in the environment Industry 4.0. The analysis of the research led to finally specifying 16 courses (<https://msie4.ait.ac.th/msie-4-0-pilot-testing-courses/>) implemented within the framework of engineering second cycle degree studies. A team of a few persons from various countries worked on each course. It allowed adjusting contents to expected learning effects which were

the most important in the process of developing the curriculum. Such a value system was conditioned with the universality of teaching. Irrespectively of the market in which a student will potentially work, he or she will have skills and competences to work in the environment Industry 4.0. Prepared courses were also subject to testing as a tool allowing improving their weaknesses and reinforcing strengths. The whole process is subject to continuous verification by persons experienced in the scope of the quality control. Such activities allow ongoing corrective actions and ensure continuity of works. Additional advantage of developing such curricula constitutes the global view on the needs of all participants of the world labour and education market. Then, mental boundaries do not exist and each individual person perceiving the contemporary world differently sees the same objective - good future.

At the Department of Management of the Czestochowa University of Technology, all faculties must obtain approval of local business representatives in order to be proceeded. Cyclicity of meetings of the Department authorities with the so-called Advisory Board of Business Representatives allows listening to the voice of employers and their needs on an ongoing basis. Such measures enable updating already existing curricula so that they evolve in correlation with business trends. Also new faculties are proposed by local entrepreneurs. The voice of employees and students is equally important. Both groups participate in works of various committees operating at the Department, which allows stakeholders to co-develop the environment of work and education so that it fulfils their expectations. Continuous improvement of employees in the scope of new teaching methods and techniques, as well as measures undertaken by the Quality Committee (within the framework of the internal education quality assurance system) with co-participation of internal and external stakeholders allow ongoing development of faculties (including curricula) of studies offered at the Department of Management. Whereas, educational objectives, taken into account while developing curricula, constitute the essence of obtaining assumed qualifications and skills by the University graduate.

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